
Assessment of Awareness about Diabetes Related Retinopathy among Type 2 Diabetes Patients- A Prospective Study

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Abstract:

India, being the Diabetes capital of the world, holds more vulnerability to developing cases of Diabetes related Retinopathy (DR). DR is an irreversible condition where complete vision loss occurs. Still, with a little effort from Diabetes patients, it can be preventable, which requires good knowledge or awareness about DR. Early detection and timely management of DR can significantly reduce the risk of vision impairment. The study aimed to assess the awareness of Diabetes related Retinopathy among Diabetes Patients through an online survey.

Objective: The objectives were to interpret the association of knowledge of Diabetes related Retinopathy on Attitude and Practice, to identify the patient's related barriers to early retinal assessment, and to evaluate the patient's understanding of the available treatment for Diabetes Retinopathy. The study highlighted the need for increased awareness among Diabetes patients regarding DR and its associated risks.

Methodology: This prospective online study helped to assess the awareness of Diabetes and Diabetes retinopathy. A validated E-questionnaire was prepared with two sections and circulated through social media to get filled out. This study planned to examine the knowledge or awareness of Diabetes patients related to Diabetes related Retinopathy as a complication of Diabetes Mellitus. The study highlighted the need for increased awareness among Diabetes patients regarding DR and its associated risks. There is a need for effective educational programs to improve knowledge and awareness about DR and its complications. This could achieve through community-based health education programs, regular medical checkups, and the involvement of healthcare professionals in educating Diabetes patients.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes Mellitus, Retinopathy, Vision impairment, Health Education.

Introduction

Diabetes related Retinopathy (DR) is the most common complication of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) and is a leading cause of blindness among working-age people worldwide. Global estimates have determined that around 30% of people with Diabetes Mellitus have Diabetes related Retinopathy [1]. DR is the ocular manifestation of end-organ damage in Diabetes mellitus [2]. The estimated prevalence remains around 34.6 % (approximately 93 million individuals), and 10.2 % have an advanced stage of the disease [3]. Although up to 98% of visual loss due to DR can be prevented with early detection and treatment, once it has progressed, vision loss is permanent [4]. The annual report of National Health Service (NHS) screening programs in England 2015–2016 reported that there were 2.59 million people with Diabetes offered screening, with 2.14 million being screened (an uptake of 82.8%) with urgent referrals for proliferative DR of 7593 and routine referrals of 52,5975. India has set to emerge as the Diabetes capital of the world. According to the WHO, 31.7 million people were affected by Diabetes Mellitus in India in 2000. This figure is estimated to rise to 79.4 million by 2030, the most significant number in any nation globally. Almost two-thirds of all Type 2 and nearly all Type 1 diabetes patients will develop Diabetes related Retinopathy over time [6]. Several factors increase the risk of DR, including the long duration of the disease, glycaemic control, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, renal failure, anemia, age, puberty, and pregnancy.

Furthermore, the Diabetes related Retinopathy knowledge level increases the incidence of DR in young women [7]. Worldwide, DM is a leading cause of blindness due to its ocular complications [8]. It is estimated that up to 84.5% of the patients with DM who have had the disease for more than 20 years will develop Diabetes related Retinopathy [8,9,10]. In addition to that, some patients didn't visit the ophthalmologist for the routine annual eye exam in the past year [11,12]. Awareness of DM and DR, along with their health impacts and treatment, can motivate patients to pursue appropriate eye care and may assist in dealing with visual impairment. In addition, for early diagnosis and treatment of DR, it is crucial to have a strong awareness of DR and its risk factors [13]. There is a lack of studies to assess the level of knowledge about DR among Diabetes patients and find associated factors with low DR awareness in India. The primary goal of this study is to determine the DR knowledge and its association with diabetes control among Diabetes patients [14].

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted online to evaluate the awareness of Diabetes and Diabetes retinopathy. The study lasted for six months, from April 2020 to September 2020. A questionnaire was developed specifically for this study and was tested on a limited population. Based on the feedback received, necessary modifications were made to the questionnaire. The questionnaire was then prepared and validated, consisting of two sections. The first section aimed to gather information about the socio-demographic factors of the respondents, such as their name, age, educational status, and marital status. The second section comprised 15 questions about knowledge, awareness, and attitude toward the disease. The study received approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee. The study included both genders and participants with type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus were eligible to participate. The study set the minimum age requirement at 16 years old. Psychiatric patients, individuals with eye disorders, and those with gestational diabetes were excluded from the study.

Results and Discussion

According to our study Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 131 (65%) were Male and 70(35%) were Female (Table 1). Naif, et al., 2018 [16] conducted a study to assess DR knowledge and its association with diabetes control among Type 2 Diabetes patients. In their study out of 253 patients, 64% were male and 36% were female diabetes patients. In our study out of 201 Diabetes patients, 79 (39%) belonged to the age group of 50-69 and 61 (30%) belonged to the age group of 40-49, 36(18%) belonged to the age group of 29-39, 14(8%) belonged to the age group of above 60 and 11 (5%) belonged to the age group of 18-28. The majority of Diabetes patients were belonging to the age group of 50-59. Bakkar, et al., 2017 [17] conducted a study on awareness of Diabetes related Retinopathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Jordan. In their study majority of Diabetes patients belong to the age group of 40-60.

According to our study Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 150 (75%) were employed and 28 (14%) were Unemployed, 16 (8%) were Retired, 7 (3%) were students (Table 1). Sami H, et al., 2018 [15] conducted a study on awareness of Diabetes related Retinopathy among people with diabetes in Jeddah. In their study, 68% of the Diabetes patients belonged to the category of employed.

According to our study Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 148 (73.6%) were diagnosed at the age of 31-40 years and 34 (17%) were diagnosed at the age of 41-50 years, 11 (5.4%) were diagnosed at the age of 20-30 years (Table 1). Most participants were diagnosed at the age of 31-41-year age. Bakkar, et al., 2017 [17] conducted a study on awareness of Diabetes related Retinopathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Jordan. In their study majority of the Diabetes patients are diagnosed at the age of 35-50 years.

Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 49 (24.3%) visited Doctor for regular check-ups and 13 (6.4%) were not going for regular Doctor check-ups and 139 (69.3%) visited the doctor only when required. Naif, et al., 2018 [16] conducted a study to assess DR knowledge and its association with diabetes control among Type 2 Diabetes patients. In their study, 48% of the population stated that they only visit their doctor in an emergency.

In our study Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 40 persons (20%) were doing regular exercises and 161 (80%) were not doing regular exercises Muhammad, et al.,2018 [27] conducted a study about an assessment of KAP towards Diabetes and Diabetes related Retinopathy in a Sub-urban town of Karachi. In their study, 67.9% of patients were not doing regular exercises.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Details

Factor	Value	N= 201	Percentage
Age	18 - 28	11	5%
	29 - 39	36	18%
	40 - 49	61	30%
	50 - 59	79	39%
	60 and above	14	8%
Gender	Male	131	65%
	Female	70	35%
Marital Status	UN-Married	11	5%
	Married	190	95%
Occupation	Student	150	75%
	Employed	28	14%
	Unemployed	7	3%
	Retried	16	8%
Age of Diagnosis of Diabetes	20-30 years	11	5.4%
	31-40 years	148	73.6%
	41-50 years	34	17%
	50 years	8	4%
Do you visit your Doctor for Regular Check-up	Yes	49	24.3%
	No	13	6.4%
	SOS	139	69.3%
Do you exercise regularly?	Yes	40	20%
	No	161	80%

Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 90 (45%) were stated eye checkups required only when their vision was affected, 64 (32%) were stated yearly once frequent eye check-ups required, 30 (15%) were stated 6 months once frequent eye check-ups required, 17 (8%) were stated 2 years once frequent eye check- [17] up required (Figure 1). Bakkar, et al., 201 conducted a study on awareness of Diabetes related Retinopathy among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Jordan. In their study, 54.5% were stated that eye check-ups required once they feel unwell.

FIGURE 1: FREQUENCY OF EYE CHECKUPS

Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 64(32%) made their first eye check-up after 5 years of diagnosis, 30(15%) made their first eye check-up at the time of diabetes diagnosis, 17(8%) were made their first eye check-up only if there was a symptom. Muhammad, et al., 2018 [27] conducted a study about an assessment of KAP towards Diabetes and Diabetes related Retinopathy in a Suburban town of Karachi. In their study, 58% of the patients stated that they made their first eye check-up when there was a symptom present.

According to our study Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 100(50%) were getting information from family or friends, 67(33%) got information from a doctor or pharmacist, 18(9%) got information from other sources and 16(8%) got information from books or internet. Manal, et al., 2020 [28] conducted a study on Awareness, knowledge, and practices related to Diabetes related Retinopathy among Diabetes patients in primary healthcare centers in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. In their study majority of the population, 162(58%) stated that the source of information about DR was doctors.

Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 104(52%) stated that they don't know about the available treatment for DR, 72(36%) stated that control of diabetes would be the treatment for DR, 18(9%) said the medication would be the treatment and 7(3%) said surgery would be the treatment for DR. Rani PK, et al., 2008 [18] conducted a study on Knowledge of diabetes and Diabetes related Retinopathy among rural populations in India, and the influence of knowledge of Diabetes related Retinopathy on attitude and practice. In their study most of the population 382(53.2%) stated that good control of diabetes would be the treatment for DR.

Out of 201 Diabetes patients, 138(68.5%) said lack of information was the reason for not performing the retinal examination, 56(28%) said lack of time was the reason for not performing the retinal examination, 4(2%) said the cost of the test was the reason and 2(1%) said living in a remote area was the reason for not performing retinal examination (Figure 2). Naif, et al., 2018 [16] conducted a study to assess DR knowledge and its association with diabetes control among Type 2 Diabetes patients. In their study, 49.3% of the patients stated that lack of information was the reason for not performing retinal examination.

FIGURE 2: REASON FOR NOT PERFORMING RETINAL EXAMINATION

The Global prevalence of DR among Diabetes patients is estimated to be 34.6%. The prevalence of diabetes in the rural Indian population was 10.4% (95% CI 10.39% to 10.42%); the prevalence of Diabetes retinopathy, among patients with diabetes mellitus, was 10.3% (95% CI 8.53% to 11.97%). More than 12% of those suffering from DR for 30 years or more are blind [19]. The pathogenesis of DR is multifactorial but is primarily due to the metabolic effects of chronic hyperglycaemia, which result in dramatic vascular changes and subsequently leads to retinal injury and ischemia [20]. Most patients who develop DR have no symptoms until the very late stages, by which time it may be too late for effective treatment [21,22,23] Proliferative retinopathy incident was more likely associated with less educated women. American Diabetes Association (ADA) guidelines recommend screening for retinopathy at the time of diagnosis of T2D and then annually after that [24].

In our study majority of participants, 111 (55%) think that there is no relationship between retinopathy and diabetes mellitus on the other hand 90 (44%) are aware of diabetes-induced retinopathy. A significant result of our study is that an increased number of participants 130 (65%) are not aware that diabetes can lead to permanent or temporary blindness only a few 71 (35%) are aware of it.

Our study reveals that 143 (72%) of participants have not done eye checkups only 58 (28%) of participants have undergone eye checkups since last year. Most of the participants 110 (55%) think that there is no need to do regular screening of the eyes if both their eyes are good only 91 (45%) were aware that regular screening of the eye is necessary. A heightened participant of 108 (54%) thinks that control of their glycaemic level can prevent Diabetes related Retinopathy on the other hand 93 (46%) think controversy.

A significant increase of 158 (79%) participants think that Diabetes patients may have eye problems at the same time of Diabetes diagnosis, but a least 43 (21%) think controversy. 141 (70%) think that Diabetes related Retinopathy is not treatable well 60 (30%) of participants think it is treatable. 137 (68%) of participants think that seeking an optometrist is enough for eye problems but 64 (32%) think that for people with diabetes is necessary to see an ophthalmologist for further worsening of eye condition.

A major significant result of our study is that 181 (90%) of people have Diabetes related Retinopathy in their family means that there is an urgent need to create awareness about Diabetes related Retinopathy with the least participant of 20 (10%) doesn't have Diabetes related Retinopathy in their family but that too which was not appreciable.

TABLE 2: AWARENESS OF DIABETES RETINOPATHY

S.No	Questions	Response	
		Yes (%)	No (%)
1.	Do you think there is a relationship between Retinopathy and DM?	90(44)	111(55)
2.	Do you think diabetes mellitus may lead to blindness?	71(35)	130(65)
3.	Have your eyes been checked by a doctor last year?	58(28)	143(72)
4.	No need for the regular screen for DR if both eyes are good?	91(45)	110(55)
5.	Do you think good control of Diabetes might prevent DR?	93(46)	108(54)
6.	Can a Diabetes patient have eye problems at the same time as a Diabetes diagnosis?	43(21)	158(79)
7.	Do you think Diabetes related Retinopathy is a treatable condition?	60(30)	141(70)
8.	Do you think seeing an optometrist (regular eyeglass store) is enough for people with diabetes?	64(32)	137(68)
9.	Does anyone in your family have Diabetes Retinopathy?	20(10)	181(90)

Some previously published studies reported that DR knowledge and awareness are poor among people. A study conducted in Turkey showed that patients with Diabetes for more than 10 years were more likely to be aware of Diabetes related Retinopathy [25]. Similarly, in our study, Diabetes for more than 10 years was more likely to be aware and more likely to have regular eye check-up annually. In our study, more than 45 % stated that there is no need for regular doctor checkups. In our study, more than 100 people stated that they didn't check their eyes for the past year.

A Japanese study showed that more than 98% of patients were aware of DR, but only 69.5% visited the ophthalmologist routinely [26]. This could be explained by a gap between the level of awareness and practice among people with diabetes, and that is why focusing on knowledge alone is insufficient in health awareness, it should be along with behavioral practice to make dramatic changes in improving patient compliance and self-care [28].

Limitation:

Our study limitations were that our study was a single centre, and our sample size is slightly under recommended sample size. Study strengths, participants were interviewed and helped by our researchers at a specialized Endocrinology clinic and using a score that represents a sum of questions related to DR rather than using a single question to decide awareness status. Though this study reveals awareness about Diabetes related Retinopathy it also has some limitations. The study duration was short, since this study was performed online, we could not reach many of the unprivileged people suffering from DM, Sample size was smaller than expected and the response was not made in our presence, so the responses could be biased.

Conclusion

This research article aimed to assess the level of awareness about Diabetes related Retinopathy among Diabetes patients. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the current knowledge and understanding of Diabetes related Retinopathy among individuals living with diabetes. The results indicate a significant gap in awareness regarding the potential risks and consequences of Diabetes related Retinopathy among Diabetes patients. Despite the high prevalence of diabetes and its associated ocular complications, the study reveals a lack of knowledge about the condition, its symptoms, and the importance of regular eye examinations.

The implications of these findings are profound, as early detection and timely intervention play a crucial role in preventing vision loss and improving long-term outcomes for individuals with Diabetes retinopathy. The lack of awareness identified in this study highlights the urgent need for targeted educational programs and awareness campaigns to enhance knowledge and promote regular eye screenings among Diabetes patients. Addressing this knowledge gap requires a collaborative effort from healthcare professionals, policymakers, and patient advocacy groups. By increasing awareness and promoting regular eye examinations, we can ensure that Diabetes patients receive appropriate eye care and reduce the burden of Diabetes related Retinopathy on individuals and healthcare systems. Also, this study underscores the importance of raising awareness about Diabetes related

Retinopathy among Diabetes patients. By prioritizing educational initiatives that empower individuals living with diabetes to take proactive measures in protecting their vision and overall health, we can significantly reduce the prevalence and impact of Diabetes related Retinopathy and improve the quality of life for millions of individuals worldwide.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors of this research article declare no potential conflicts of interest.

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The research work adhered to the highest ethical standards throughout the research process. Approval Certificate Number: JKKNCPE/ETHICS_PRACTICE/020PDS0, Dated 17.04.2020.

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